

Employees Performance Appraisal of Chettinad Cement Gulbarga

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Abstract- Chettinad Cement Corporation Limited (CCCL) incorporated in 1962 and part of the Chettinad group, is engaged in the manufacture of cement since 1967. The group has varied business interests in cement, engineering, logistics, transportation, hospitals and other sectors. CCCL operates four cement manufacturing facilities situated at Puliur, Karikkali and Ariyalur in the state of Tamil Nadu (TN) and Gulbarga in the state of Karnataka. As on March 31, 2014, the company's aggregate installed capacity stood at 11 million tonnes per annum (MTPA). CCCL has availability of thermal – based captive power plants (CPP) in all its manufacturing facilities. The company also possesses captive thermal power plants with an aggregate capacity of 135 MW of power generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is questionable where it was first found that a mix of hydrate non- water driven lime and a pozzolan produces a water driven blend, yet cement produced using such combination was first utilized for huge scope by roman architects. They utilized both normal pozzolans (trass or pumice) and fake pozzolans (ground block or earthenware) in the cements. Numerous fantastic instances of designs produced using these cements are as yet standing. Prominently the enormous solid arch of the pantheon in Rome and the gigantic Shower of Caracalla. The huge arrangement of roman water channels additionally utilized pressure driven cement. The utilization of primary cement vanished in middle age Europe. Albeit frail pozzolanic cements kept on being utilized as a center fills in stone dividers and sections.

II. FUTURE GROWTH AND PROSPECTS

With developing interest for cement inside India and South East Asian nations, Chettinad Cement is good to go for extension. It had chosen to extend its points of view by beginning another green field cement plant of 0.9 million tons limit for every annum with an expected expense of about Rs 350 crore. Chettinad Cement will commission a 2.5 million tons every year (mtpa) cement plant in North Karnataka in the current year and has finished designs to venture into Andhra Pradesh

The Karnataka unit will check Chettinad Cement's topographical development outside Tamil Nadu and will give it market venture into Maharashtra, where it intends to set up a pounding unit of about 1.5 million tons every year, as indicated by Mr M.A.M.R. Muthiah, Chettinad Groups Managing director Expansion

The organization has firm intends to grow its 11.50 mtpa creation limit by around 15 million tons with 7.5 mtpa each in Karnataka and in Andhra Pradesh, where it intends to dispatch its tasks with a securing of a 1.5 mtpa unit, aside from a Greenfield cement.

It has gone into a concurrence with the Andhra Pradesh Government, which is to work with the undertakings in which the organization will contribute over Rs 1,500 crore.

- Objectives of Performance Appraisal
- To audit the performance of the workers

over a span of time.

- To judge the difference between the real and the desired performance.
- To help the administration in practicing organizational control.
- Helps to fortify the relationship and correspondence between prevalent – subordinates and the board – workers.
- To analyze the qualities and short comings of the people in order to recognize the preparation and advancement needs of the future.

Functions of Employee Performance Reviews, Employee Performance Appraisal

Performance audits (additionally alluded to as execution examinations and Performance Appraisals) serve many useful purposes for any type of organization no matter how large or small. These functions include;

- Basis for Performance Review

The purpose of a performance appraisal is to provide regular feedback to all employees at all levels in an organization. One of the way this is achieved is with the use of competencies. Competencies permit an association to characterize what occupation activities and qualities are adequately significant to be measured. This likewise permits workers to get what activities are significant in their work and in case they are meeting or surpassing assumptions they were hired for an performance audit helps in figuring out who the vital workers in an association are. It also brings out difficulties for the administration to keep the remainder of the representatives spurred and guarantee that they continue to work at ideal levels. Also, it permits the administration to receive certain procedures to address the conduct of the ineffectively performing employees

- Setting up of Work Goals

Performance Appraisal present a chance for the administration to examine work duties and concede to shared objectives with the

representatives. The worker and his chief also discuss the employee's objective start of each year or review period. Manager said their representatives in recognizing their goals by causing them to comprehend the connection between their work and the departmental /organizational goals. The manager along with the employee must likewise work on characterizing the estimation to be utilized for the assessment of every one of these destinations. This implies that both the workers and their chiefs should consent to the targets and the assessment strategies associated with them. Representatives ought not lay out unreasonable objectives, as this will lead to failure and problems with the management in the future vital for the worker ought to be distinguished and orchestrated during this cycle. Elements of Worker Execution Surveys, Representative Performance Appraisal.

- Purpose of Performance Appraisal

Performance Appraisal is being polished in 90% of the associations around the world. Self-evaluation and potential examination likewise structure a piece of the presentation evaluation measures.

- Roles in the Performance Appraisal process

Reporting Manager

- Provide criticism to the commentator/HOD on the representatives' social attributes demonstrated in the PMS Strategy Manual
- Ensures that worker knows about the standardization/ Performance appraisal process
- Address worker concerns/inquiries on execution rating, in interview with the commentator
- Analyst (Announcing Supervisor's Revealing Administrator)
- Discuss with the reporting managers on the behavioral traits of all the employees for whom he/she is the reviewer.

- Where required, autonomously evaluate representatives for the said conduct characteristics; such appraisals may require gathering information straight forwardly from other important workers HOD.
- Presents the proposed Execution Rating for each representative of his/her capacity to the Normalization committee.
- HR Head
- Secretary to the normalization committee
- Assists HOD's/Announcing Administrators in conveying the presentation rating of the multitude of workers

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Performance Appraisal is the way toward getting, investigating and recording data about the overall worth of a representative. The focal point of the presentation examination is estimating and working on the real execution of the representative and furthermore the future capability of the worker. Its point is to gauge what a representative does. Representative execution was assessed by utilizing conventional techniques which do not fill the genuine need of performance

3.1 Need for Performance Appraisal

- It can be utilized as a reason for remuneration distributions i.e., compensation builds, advancements and other rewards.
- It can be utilized for distinguishing regions where advancement endeavors like preparing and development are required. Performance Appraisal helps in distinguishing those deficiencies where advancement is needed.
- Selection interaction can be created based on a legitimate solid and biasfree performance appraisal system.
- Mentally, Performance Appraisal is an integral asset with gigantic effect on, the

workers and, through them on the association.

3.2 Objectives of the Performance Appraisal

- To study existing Performance Appraisal rehearses in the organization.
- To devise an appropriate Performance Appraisal Performa for building up Appraisal framework/measure
- To consider and comprehend the effect of the examination framework presented in the organization.

3.3 Scope of Performance Appraisal

- Provide workers a superior comprehension of their job and duties.
- Increment certainty through perceiving qualities while distinguishing preparing requirements to further develop shortcomings.
- Improve on working connections and correspondence among managers and subordinates. Increment obligation to authoritative objectives; form workers into future managers. Aid staff choices like advancements or apportioning rewards.
- Permit time for self-reflection, self-evaluation and individual objective setting.

3.4 Research Methodology

Research Methodology is the interaction of methodical examination of any administration issue is to manage research plan, information assortment strategy, inspecting plan, testing technique.

“Research” means Logical and deliberate quest for appropriate data on a particular theme. Examination is a careful investigation or on the other hand request particularly through look for new realities in any part of

information. Exploration contains characterizing and reclassifying issues, figuring speculation or recommended arrangement; gathering, sorting out and assessing information, making derivations and arriving at resolutions; and finally cautiously testing the ends to decide if they fit the planning theory.

“Methodology” is characterized as the investigation of strategies by which we acquire information it manages psychological cycles forced on examination to the issue emerging from the idea of its topic.

3.5 Hypothesis of the Performance Appraisal

- The conduct of workers doesn't change after performance appraisal.
- There is no relationship between execution framework and addition in salary.
- Performance of representatives doesn't work on after performance appraisal.
- There is no relationship between execution examination and fulfillment level of workers.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. OF ATTENDANCE ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	11	0.55
AGREE	08	0.44
NEUTRAL	02	0.1
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

2. IMPACT OF EMPLOYEES PERFORMANCE ON PRODUCTIVITY

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	10	0.5
AGREE	10	0.5
NEUTRAL	00	00
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

3. IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE TIME MANAGEMENT ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	07	0.35
AGREE	11	0.55
NEUTRAL	02	0.1
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

4. EFFECTIVE TEAM WORK AND COLLABORATION

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	06	0.3
AGREE	08	0.4
NEUTRAL	06	0.3
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

5. IMPACT OF QUALITY

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	04	0.2
AGREE	10	0.5
NEUTRAL	06	0.3
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

6. IMPACT OF ACCOUNTABILITY ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	07	0.35
AGREE	07	0.35
NEUTRAL	06	0.3
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	00

7. IMPACT OF CREATIVITY AND INITIATIVE ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	03	0.15
AGREE	13	0.65
NEUTRAL	04	0.3
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00

DISAGREE		
TOTAL	20	100

8. IMPACT OF SAFETY CONCISENESS ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	05	0.25
AGREE	10	0.5
NEUTRAL	05	0.25
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

9. IMPACT OF REQUIRED SKILL ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	10	0.5
AGREE	09	0.45
NEUTRAL	01	0.05
DISAGREE	00	00
STRONGLY DISAGREE	00	00
TOTAL	20	100

10. IMPACT OF RECOGNITION AND REWARD ON PERFORMANCE

OPTION	NO.OF RESPONSE	PERFORMANCE IN %
STRONGLY AGREE	10	0.5
	08	0.4

AGREE		
NEUTRAL	02	0.1
DISAGRE E	00	00
STRONGL Y DISAGRE E	00	00
TOTAL	20	00

V. FINDINGS

- The Existing performance appraisal methods are not satisfactory.
- The evaluation of performance is not being done systematic format
- Managers are not being trained and enough competent to design new appraisal system/procedure & take use of the performance appraisal for future oriented activities.
- Chettinad kallur plant is a production unit of cement, where it's revenue and development of organization of this organization is mainly depends on the employees only, hence employees are honest to their duties and responsibilities
- In chettinad the time management, team work, collaboration, communication between all levels of management is good & in a proper way. For this reason only it's possible to run organization smoothly.
- In Chettinad comment there is average level of goal oriented job/task. Job analysis, Job specification & job description is not adopted by the HR/ADM. Dept.
- Average number of employee's like to learn or wishes to get knowledge regarding their job & they feel that through proper knowledge of job the efficiency level will automatically increases.
- More number of peoples looking towards judgmental aspects related to evaluation of performance.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

- Chettinad cement is a regular production industry, so employees have to be on work for all 12 months If employees are ready to work for full season then the organization automatically earn the profit & employees also get extra benefits from this.
- Each employees of the organization try to set their individual goal towards achieving the overall organization goal.
- Conduct the training programme for employees related to their job, it helps in improving the organization
- Evaluate the performance of each and every employees of the organization on regular basis and provide the proper guidelines to them for improvement.
- Main goal of the chettinad organization is to earn more profit. If the chettinad cement should taken care of employees in terms of their safety, expectations etc then it is easy to reach the organization goal
- It's my sugesstion that's chettinad cement should set a standard for performance appraisal of employee and measure evey 6 month and keep a award and reward for the employee who meets the standard. And those who lag give training to them

CONCLUSION

It is truth that no work is completed in itself. In fact, completion of one job isactually the beginning of another job. Likewise, performance Appraisal is neverending process. It is essential for personal & professional development.This project has been considering all possible aspects mentioned in the projectbooklet. The project is made very clear and precise with the help of the relevantdata gathered from the company, company website & through various annexure.In the concluding remark of my project report, I would like to state

that at Chettinad cement are considered as most valuable assets & strength for sustained growth & development of the company. They believe in investing continuously in human resource for their growth. The company is led by young professionals. They have an open work environment which is achievement oriented.

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